

Impact of School Communication on Teachers' Job Performance in Senior Secondary Schools in Suleja, Niger State

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ABSTRACT

The study assessed the impact of school communication on teachers' job performance in Senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State. The study was guided by two research questions with corresponding hypotheses. descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study. The population of this study consisted of 2605 teachers. The sample size of the study consisted of 568 respondents. The instrument used for data collection was the 'Questionnaire on the Impact of Communication on Teacher Job Performance (QICTJP)'. The instrument yielded the validity index of 0.70. The reliability index of 0.72 was obtained. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used for data analysis while the Analysis of Variance was used for testing the hypothesis. The findings of the study showed that there is a significant impact of upward communication on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State and there is a significant impact of downward communication on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State. One of the recommendations of the study was that principals of secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State should be periodically subjected to series of training through workshops, conferences and seminars to enable them acquire the useful skills and knowledge needed to promote upward communication in the school system.

Keywords: School Communication, Teachers' Job Performance, Upward Communication and Downward Communication

Received: 22 March. 2024

Revised: 2 April 2024

Final Accepted: 11 April 2024

Introduction

The survival of any institution depends on the pattern of communication. Communication serves as the bedrock for achieving the stated school goals and objectives. Without proper communication in the school system among students, teachers and principals, disharmony may occur in the process of coordinating the activities of a school because in most cases, ineffectiveness in school management normally arise due to difficulty in the exchange of information among the various members of a school. Every principal in secondary school is tasked with the responsibility of the day-to-day management of a school. In the secondary school system, the role of a principal is to communicate in a manner that would induce the behaviour of teachers positively to improve the quality of teaching-learning situation in the school system. The attainment of the objectives of secondary schools required proper communication of principals with teachers on their job schedules and other school policies. Bello (2018) described communication as the exchange of information and transmission of ideas in organization to enhance the attainment of the stipulated objectives.

In the view of Stephen (2019), communication is a critical factor in directing and mobilizing the labour force towards the achievement of the goals and objectives of an institution. It is the avenue through which the basic management functions are performed because school managers direct the affairs of their schools, co-ordinate, plan and control through series of communication patterns. School communication takes place between among principals, teaching and non-teaching staff, students, community members and other stakeholders. The goals of secondary schools are shared by the principals who are the heads of secondary schools with the relevant individuals within the school system through communication. As such, without proper school communication, it may be difficult for teachers to be informed about their responsibilities in a manner that would improve their job performance (Ubeku, 2015).

The pattern of communication adopted by school managers may help to determine the nature of interaction and peaceful atmosphere needed for effective teaching and learning because it directs the behaviour and the activities of both staff and students in the school setting. It is the responsibility of every principal to adopt the forms of that would help to realign and modify the

Received: 22 March, 2024

Revised: 2 April 2024

Final Accepted: 11 April 2024

attitude of teachers, students and community members towards the achievement of set targets in a school (Oshoke, 2017). Teachers are the most important set of people in the educational system as without them, the education system may not achieve its goals and objectives. The importance of teacher's job performance necessitate the identification of factors that would help to enhance their job performance. Job performance means the situation of accomplishing a given task (Nwosu, 2017). Teacher job performance refers to the duties undertaken by a teacher in the school system with the aim of realizing the stated goals and objectives. Teachers' job performance could be determined using the level of their satisfaction, attitudes to work, commitment, determination and spirit of enthusiasm. Job performance is important to enhance the quality of instructional delivery in the school setting. The pattern of communication between principals and teachers may help to enhance the effective job performance among teachers or render them ineffective. When teachers are not properly informed about their job description, they may get wrong instruction that would lead to poor job performance. However, principals have different patterns of communication when sharing their ideas, thoughts, resolutions and school policies with teachers. Generally, communication in secondary schools occurs in three forms which include downward communication, upward communication and horizontal communication (Iyala, 2018).

Downward communication involves the flow of rules, policies and procedures from the top level to the lowest level of the school system. In other words, communication from superiors to subordinates in a chain of command is seen as downward communication. This form of communication in a secondary school entails the transfer of information from the principal, to vice-principals, teachers, non-teaching staff and students. In the downward communication, instructions on job performance are passed from the higher to lower levels of the school organizational structure. Through downward communication, information on new strategies and school goals would be made available to teachers by their principals to enable them undertake their assigned responsibilities diligently. The downward flow of information provides a channel for directives and instructions to members of an institution (Solaja, Faremi, & Adesina (2015). However, such instructions may be distorted if it is not properly transmitted to the receivers. A distorted information lacks the ability to produce good results. This pattern of communication

Received: 22 March, 2024

Revised: 2 April 2024

Final Accepted: 11 April 2024

flow would be used by principals to transmit work-related information to teachers to enable them understand what they are expected to do within a given period of time. Differences in experience, knowledge, levels of authority and status between principals and teachers may lead to wrong assumptions that would lead to poor job performance due to misunderstanding and misinterpretation of instructions by principals regarding the job description of teachers. The principle of downward communication discourage principals from communicating in an unambiguous manner with teachers in order to ensure that teachers clearly understand their assigned responsibilities and perform them diligently (Anderson, 2018).

Another form of communication that would induce teachers job performance is upward communication flows. In the school system, upward communication is the transfer of information from the lower level of staff to the top level such as from teachers to principals in the case of secondary school setting (Canary, 2021). Upward communication involves the reports on tasks performance, expression of grievances, complaints and other information from teachers to principals in secondary schools. In secondary school system, principals who encourage upward communication may promote cooperation, gain respect from teachers, secure teachers' support, increase the confidence of teachers, reduce confusion and frustration among teachers. The major content of upward communication include request for instructional materials, proposals, complaints for poor working conditions, appeals, reports and other information directed from teachers to principals. Principals that encourage upward communication channels would enhance the job satisfaction of teachers. It is expected that principals operate open-door policy to enable teachers feel free and approach them with the problems that hinder their teaching effectiveness. Upward communication may help to inform school management about the challenges, levels of performance and other issues that may prevent job effectiveness among teachers (Nkechi & Felix, 2018).

Principals are required to communicate the school policies and programmes to teachers to enable them have ideas of the jobs they are to performed to achieve the goals and objectives of a school. Through proper school communication, teachers would express themselves to the principals about the nature of their job responsibilities and genral working conditions. Umoh (2023)

Received: 22 March. 2024

Revised: 2 April 2024

Final Accepted: 11 April 2024

suggested that a two-way communication channel is required for both the principals and teachers to facilitate teachers' professional growth through effective job performance. It is the responsibility of every principals to encourage a two-way communication channels which allows feedback to and fro the staff but when such process is discouraged, teachers may not have access to adequate instruction and information needed to undertake their assigned responsibilities diligently. The ability of the principal to communicate effectively would help teachers to participate actively in the instructional delivery activities of their schools. This study was design to assess the impact of communication on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State.

Statement of the Problem

In recent times, there is seem to be public complaints on the decline of students academic performance in both internal and external examinations in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State. Such decline may be attributted to the level of low teachers' job commitment and poor job performance. Principals who supposed to assign, guide and direct teachers to undertake their assigned responsibilities successfully seem to be too hostile and unapproachable for teachers to communicate the challenges they encounter in the process of performing their teaching jobs to them. This may lead to poor upward communication with negative effect on the overall performance of teachers. Principals without appropriate communication skills may provide wrong instruction when assigning responsibilities to teachers. The inappropriate instruction may influence frequent misunderstanding with the consequences of making teachers to be in the state of confusion, thereby making mistakes regularly. Teachers who experience the above difficulty may not be effective to perform their teaching responsibilities successfully. Such teachers may be easily frustrated and develop low morale that would lead to poor self-motivation and low productivity.

When there are communication gaps in the school system, the various staff and units of a school tend to operate in isolation and perhaps experience conflict that would hinder the general objectives of teaching and learning in an institution. Authoritative principals may discourage upward communication in a manner that would lead to breakdown in communication and influence misunderstanding, confusion and frustration among teachers and prevent them from

Received: 22 March. 2024

Revised: 2 April 2024

Final Accepted: 11 April 2024

carrying out their teaching tasks effectively. Some principals seem to withhold vital information regarding the school policies from teachers thereby making teachers to rely on rumours or grapevine information to perform their tasks. In the school system, teachers cannot plan or teach properly in the absence of adequate and vital information concerning teaching and learning. This study assessed the impact of communication on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State.

Purpose of the Study

The main objective of this study was to assess the impact of school communication on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State. The specific objectives of the study included the following:

1. To determine the impact of upward communication on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State?
2. To ascertain the impact of downward communication on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State.

Research Questions

The following research questions have been generated for the purpose of this study:

1. What is the impact of upward communication on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State?
2. What is the impact of downward communication on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State.

Hypotheses

The study tested the following hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance:

HO₁. There is no significant impact upward communication and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State.

HO₂. There is no significant impact downward communication and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State.

Research Methodology

The study was guided by the descriptive survey research design. The population of this study consisted of 2605 teachers obtained from all the public senior secondary schools in the eight Area Inspectorate Offices in Suleija, Niger State. The sample size of this study consisted of 568 teachers drawn from 24 secondary schools in Suleja Local Government Area of Niger State. The researcher developed an instrument for data collection from the respondents. The instrument used for data collection was tagged 'Questionnaire on the Impact of Communication on Teacher Job Performance (QICTJP)'. The questionnaire consisted of 14 items designed based on 4-point modified Likert's rating scale given as follows: 4=Strongly Agree (SA), 3=Agree (A), 2=Disagree (D), 1= Strongly Disagree (SD). The instrument produced the validity index of 0.70. The reliability index of 0.72 was obtained which means that the instrument was suitable for data collection. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using the One-way Analysis of Variance (ANAOVA).

Results

Research Question 1: What is the impact of upward communication on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis Showing the Upward Communication and Teachers’ Job Performance

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	Std. 6	Decision
1.	Teachers are afraid of communicating with the principal which limit their job performance.	68	50	220	230	2.20	0.70	Disagree
2.	Teachers freely express their grievances to principals.	84	60	184	240	2.32	0.66	Disagree
3.	Principal gives teachers opportunity to seek clarification about conflicting issues from him to help and improve the job efficiency of teachers.	70	105	208	185	2.41	0.73	Disagree
4.	Suggestions from teachers that would enhance their job performance go directly to the principal.	68	110	206	184	2.18	0.81	Disagree
5.	Teachers undertake their job diligently because they are granted access to report the difficulty they encounter in performing their job to the principal.	137	220	167	44	2.55	0.65	Agree
6.	Principal welcomes complaints from teachers that would promote effective job performance from teachers.	88	40	230	210	2.25	0.78	Disagree
7.	Teachers perform their job properly because they have direct communication with the principal.	67	85	210	206	2.35	0.74	Disagree
Cluster Mean						2.32	0.72	Disagree

Table 1 shows that item 1 has the mean score of 2.20 and standard deviation of 0.70, item 2 has the mean score of 2.32 and standard deviation of 0.66, item 3 has the mean score of 2.41 and standard deviation of 0.73, item 4 has the mean score of 2.18 and standard deviation of 0.81, item 5 has the mean score of 2.55 and standard deviation of 0.65, item 6 has the mean score of

2.25 and standard deviation of 0.78 while item 7 has the mean score of 2.35 and standard deviation of 0.74. The details of the analysis indicated that the cluster mean of 2.32 is below the scale mean of 2.50, the results showed that there is poor upward communication that leads to teachers' job performance in in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State.

Research Question 2: What is the impact of downward communication on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis Showing the Relationship between Downward Communication and Teachers' Job Performance

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	Std. σ	Decision
8.	Principal communicates politely with teachers to improve their job performance.	53	75	205	235	2.10	0.79	Disagree
9.	Principal encourages upward communication to motivate teachers to undertake their job properly.	92	94	169	247	2.20	0.62	Disagree
10.	Principals do not delay in passing instructions on teaching responsibilities to teachers.	88	110	237	177	2.30	0.63	Disagree
11.	There is free flow of interaction between principal and teachers.	70	106	234	192	2.35	0.60	Disagree
12.	Principal discusses the school policies with teachers on regularly.	64	133	148	257	2.40	0.75	Disagree
13.	Principal does not withhold vital information of the school that require effective job performance from teachers.	73	84	215	230	2.22	0.77	Disagree
14.	Principal possess the appropriate skills for effective communication with teachers to ease their job.	69	86	238	209	2.38	0.70	Disagree
Cluster Mean						2.27	0.69	Disagree

Table 2 showed that item 8 has the mean score of 2.10 and standard deviation of 0.79, item 9 has the mean score of 2.20 and standard deviation of 0.62, item 10 has the mean score of 2.30 and standard deviation of 0.63, item 11 has the mean score of 2.35 and standard deviation of 0.60, item 12 has the mean score of 2.40 and standard deviation of 0.75, item 13 has the mean score of 2.22 and standard deviation of 0.77 while item 14 has the mean score of 2.38 and standard deviation of 0.70. The details of the analysis showed that the cluster mean of 2.32 is below the scale mean of 2.50, the results showed that there is a low impact of downward communication on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant impact of upward communication on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State.

Table 3 = One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) showing the Impact of Communication on Teachers' Job Performance in Senior Secondary Schools in Suleija, Niger State

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	P
Between Groups	1381.099	18	86.319	1.735	.039	<.05; Significant
Within Groups	17063.276	550	49.747			
Total	18444.375	568				

Dfs = 16,343; p < .05 Significant

The table 3 above shows that the ANAOVA's f-calculated value of 1.735 is greater than the F-critical of 1.66 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis one was not accepted which means that upward communication has significant impact on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State (dfs = 18,550; F-calculated = 1.734, F-critical = 166; p> 0.05; Significant)

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant impact of downward communication on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State.

Table 4 = One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) showing the Impact of Downward Communication on Teachers’ Job Performance in Senior Secondary Schools in Suleija Niger State

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	P
Between Groups	872.084	18	54.505	1.690	.389	>. 05;
Within Groups	17572,291	550	51.231			Significant
Total	18444,375	568				

Dfs = 16,343; p > .05; Significant

Table 2 above shows that the F-calculated value of 1.764 is greater than the F-critical value of 1.66, this therefore means that the null hypothesis two was not accepted, hence, there is a significant impact of downward communication on teachers’ job performance in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State (dfs = 18,568; F calculated = 1.690, F-critical = 166; p> .05; Significant).

Major Findings of the Study

The summary of the major findings of the study include:

1. There is significant impact of upward communication on teachers’ job performance in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State.
2. There is significant impact of downward communication on teachers’ job performance in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State.

Discussion of the Findings

The findings of the study indicated that there is significant impact of upward communication on teachers’ job performance in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State. The findings of the study confirmed the position of Nakpodia (2015) who maintained that teachers’ performance in secondary schools is significantly dependent on the communication skills of the principals in secondary schools in Delta State. In the school system, upward communication is the transfer of information from the lower level of staff to the top level such as from teachers to principals in

Received: 22 March. 2024

Revised: 2 April 2024

Final Accepted: 11 April 2024

the case of secondary school setting. Upward communication involves the reports on tasks performance, expression of grievances, complaints and other information from teachers to principals in secondary schools. In secondary school system, principals who encourage upward communication may promote cooperation, gain respect from teachers, secure teachers' support, increase the confidence of teachers, reduce confusion and frustration among teachers. The major content of upward communication include request for instructional materials, proposals, complaints for poor working conditions, appeals, reports and other information directed from teachers to principals. Principals that encourage upward communication channels would enhance the job satisfaction of teachers. It is expected that principals operate open-door policy to enable teachers feel free and approach them with the problems that hinder their teaching effectiveness. Upward communication may help to inform school management about the challenges, levels of performance and other issues that may prevent job effectiveness among teachers.

The findings of the study further showed that there is significant impact of downward communication on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State. The findings of the research disagreed with Osakwe (2016) who submitted that to a high extent, the principals were competent in communication with teachers which help to improve their job performance in Federal Government Colleges in North Central, Nigeria. Downward communication involves the flow of rules, policies and procedures from the top level to the lowest level of the school system. In other words, communication from superiors to subordinates in a chain of command is seen as downward communication. This form of communication in a secondary school entails the transfer of information from the principal, to vice-principals, teachers, non-teaching staff and students. In the downward communication, instructions on job performance are passed from the higher to lower levels of the school organizational structure. Through downward communication, information on new strategies and school goals would be made available to teachers by their principals to enable them undertake their assigned responsibilities diligently. However, such instructions may be distorted if it is not properly transmitted to the receivers. A distorted information lacks the ability to produce good results. This pattern of communication flow would be used by principals to transmit work-related

Received: 22 March, 2024

Revised: 2 April 2024

Final Accepted: 11 April 2024

information to teachers to enable them understand what they are expected to do within a given period of time. Differences in experience, knowledge, levels of authority and status between principals and teachers may lead to wrong assumptions that would lead to poor job performance due to misunderstanding and misinterpretation of instructions by principals regarding the job description of teachers. The principle of downward communication discourage principals from communicating in an unambiguous manner with teachers in order to ensure that teachers clearly understand their assigned responsibilities and perform them diligently.

Conclusion

The study concluded that there is poor job performance by teachers in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State due to the inability of principals to encourage upward communication.

The study also concluded that principals in senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State do not properly communicate downward to the teachers to enable them perform their job effectively.

Recommendations

1. Principals of senior secondary schools in Suleija, Niger State should be periodically subjected to series of training through workshops, conferences and seminars to enable them acquire the useful skills and knowledge needed to promote upward communication in the school system.
2. The Niger State Government should ensure that there should be a policy discouraging verbal instruction from the principals to teachers, as such, all forms of downward communications should be in written form so that teachers could get clear instructions on the responsibilities assigned to them and perform their jobs diligently.

REFERENCES

- Andersoon, O. H. (2019). *Agricultural Communication Principles and Practice*, Umuahia: Lamb House Publishers
- Bello, I. S. (2018). Teachers Perception of the Principals Communication and Attitude to Work in Secondary School in Old Kaduna State. Unpublished M.Ed. Thesis, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- Canary, H. (2021). *Communication and organizational knowledge: Contemporary issues for Theory and Practice*. Florence, KY: Taylor & Francis.
- Iyala, F. E. (2018). Relationship between emotional intelligence and principals' managerial effectiveness in senior secondary schools in North Central States of Nigeria. A thesis submitted to the school of postgraduate studies, Nasarawa State University, Keffi in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of Ph.D. in Educational Administration and Planning..Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education, Nasarawa State University, Keffi.Nasarawa State.
- Nkechi, E. S., & Felix, E. I. (2018). Influence of emotional intelligence on principals' decision making skills in the management of public secondary schools of Benue State Nigeria. *Journal of Basic and Applied Research International*, 24(5), 200-207.
- Nwosu, J. C. (2017). Principals' Communication Strategies And Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State. *International Journal of Education, Learning and Development*, 5(9), 1-12.

- Oshoke, S. A. (2017). Impact of communication patterns during inspection on school performance in secondary schools in Edo State. *Journal of Educational Change*, 11(2), 157-176.
- Stephen, C. (2019). *Research Methodology in Business and Social Sciences*, Owerri: Canon.
- Solaja, O. M, Faremi, E. I., & Adesina, E. J. (2015). Exploring the Relationship between Leadership Communication Style, Personality Trait and Organizational Productivity. *Serbian Journal of Management*, 11(1), 99 – 117.
- Ubeku, T.O. (2015). *Perspectives of Communication and Instruction*: Longman. Lagos.
- Umoh, B. (2023). Supervisory and Communication Roles of Principals in Enhancing Teachers' Development in Secondary Schools in Kitui West District, Kenya. Thesis Submitted to the Faculty of Education in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree of Master of Education in the Department of Educational Administration and Planning: Catholic University of Eastern Africa.